

THE CONCEPT AND MEANING OF MANAGEMENT AND ITS BASIC
NATURE

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Annotation: This article devoted to open basic concepts of the term “management”, its meaning and features. In addition to this, in the article peculiarities of successful management in the modern world are highlighted.

Key words: *human effects, industrial world, resources of production, effective enterprise, specific objectives, Goal-oriented process, Pervasive.*

Management is universal in the modern industrial world and there is no substitute for good management. It makes human effects more productive and brings better technology, products and services to our society. It is a crucial economic resource and a life giving element in business. Without proper management, the resources of production (men, machines and materials, money) cannot be converted into production. Thus management is a vital function concerned with all aspects of the working of an organization[1]. Management is a must to accomplish desired goals through group action. It is essential to convert the disorganized resources of men, machines, materials and methods into a useful and effective enterprise. Thus management is the function of getting things done through people and directing the efforts of individuals towards a common objective.

If we look up the definition of the term “management” we can find such descriptions of this word. Management is the art of maximizing efficiency, as a social process, a method of getting things done through others a plan of action and its direction by a co-operative group moving towards a common goal. Effective utilization of available resources to achieve same objective is management.

Management is a comprehensive function of Planning, Organizing, Forecasting Coordinating, Leading, Controlling, Motivating the efforts of others to achieve specific objectives[2]. Management can precisely be called the rule – making and rule – enforcing body. According to Harold Koontz “ Management is the art of getting things done through and with formally organized groups “. According to Peter F. Drucker. “ A Multipurpose organ that manages a business and manages managers and manages workers and works “. According to J.Lundy “ Management is what management does. It is the task of planning executing and controlling “. According to Lawrence Appley “ Management is the development of people and not the direction of things“.

Management is overall the most important factor because no business runs on itself, even no momentum. Every business needs repeated stimulus which can only be provided by management. Thus, management is dynamic, life giving element without which the “ factors of production “ will remain as were factors not become “ Production “.Some experts feel that management principles and knowledge do not have universal application due to cross- culture differences. They are also of the view that same management skills can not be applied in all situations and fields and the skills are not transferable. Peter Drucker, states that “ The skill, the competence, the experience of management cannot, as such be transferred and applied to the organisation and running of other institutions . A career in management is, by itself, not a preparation for major political office or for leadership in the armed forces, the church or a university”’. It can be concluded that basic principles and functions of management are universal in nature. These can be applied in every type of organisation and in every country. The application of these principles, however may vary from person to person. The art and practice of management always varies from situations to situations and it is culture bound.

It is safe to say that an effective manager is a key ingredient for business success[3]. A manager’s job is to ensure good management in an organisation. This is achieved by learning the ins and outs of management. Thus

gain deeper insights into management we need to learn about the basic characteristics of management.

1. Goal-oriented process- An essential aspect of management is to combine individual efforts and direct them towards achieving organisational goals. These goals differ from organisation to organisation. For example, an organisation can have a profit motive whereas a social work organisation might have a goal of eradicating illiteracy among children. Management recognises these goals and aims to fulfil them.
2. Pervasive- Management is a requirement and essential for the functioning of all kinds of organisations- social, economic or political. Without management, the processes of an organisation would be chaotic and unordered. Further, it is equally essential for organisations across all countries. However, the only difference lies in the how management is implemented within an organisation.
3. Multidimensional- Management has three dimensions:
 - Work management: Every organisation exists for completion of some work. This work varies from producing clothes in clothing sector to treating patients in hospitals. Management looks at this work as goals to be achieved and works towards these goals. Further, this is done in terms of problems to be solved, decisions to be made, plans to be established, budgets to be prepared, responsibilities to be assigned and authority to be delegated.
 - Management of people: Another dimension of management is concerned with getting work done from people, by assigning work to worthy employees who can work effectively towards the realisation of organisational goals. This is achieved by ensuring that the strength is highlighted and the weakness is driven out of the equation. It further has two dimensions- a) dealing with people as individuals with diverse needs and behaviours and b) dealing with individuals perceiving them as a part of a wider group of people.

- Management of operations: As every organisation aims at the completion of work, they also have a particular product or service to provide with respect to their domain of operation. Note that this is met with the help of a production process. Management also looks after a production process of an organisation that transforms the input with the help of technology required into the output for consumption. Interestingly, this is linked to both management of work and people.
4. Continuous Process- We now know that there are various functions of management. These are- planning, organising, directing, staffing and controlling. As a matter of fact, a manager performs all these functions simultaneously. Although these functions are separate, management is concerned with performing all of them simultaneously all the time. Consequently, management is a dynamic and continuous process.
 5. Group Activity- An organisation consists of a large number of individuals having different reasons and purposes to join. Again these individual differ based on their needs and behaviours. However, it is important to realise that these diverse individuals work together towards the achievement of the organisational goals. Management diverts the individual efforts towards the right direction. Further, effective management enables all the individuals to grow and develop as their needs and opportunities change.
 6. Dynamic Function- An organisation has to adapt to the environment in order to succeed. Thus management is dynamic in nature and adapts to the ever-changing social, economic and political conditions. A famous example of this is how McDonald's had to change its menu to serve and emerge as a major fast food giant in the Indian market.
 7. Intangible Force- Management cannot be touched or it isn't tangible. However effective management can be easily felt. Evidently, if there is order instead of chaos within an organisation, the employees are happy and the organisational goals are being organised it can be easily said that there exists good management[4].

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that the concept of management has acquired special significance in the present competitive and complex business world. Efficient and purposeful management is absolutely essential for the survival of a business unit. Management concept is comprehensive and covers all aspects of business. In simple words, management means utilizing available resources in the best possible manner and also for achieving well defined objectives. It is a distinct and dynamic process involving use of different resources for achieving well defined objectives. The resources are: men, money, materials, machines, methods and markets. These are the six basic inputs in management process (six M's of management) and the output is in the form of achievement of objectives. It is the end result of inputs and is available through efficient management process.

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